

Sup. Figure 1

A

B

C

Monocytes	>48 vs 24-48 h	24-48 vs 0-24 h	>48 h	24-48 h	0-24 h
Protein Coding	54.8	82.7	75.0	80.5	74.5
Ig	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
TcR	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
lncRNA	27.4	11.8	15.3	11.6	13.1
Non-coding RNA	2.7	0.7	1.7	1.2	1.4
TEC	1.4	0.9	1.7	2.2	2.1
Pseudogene	13.7	3.6	6.0	4.5	9.0

Neutrophils	>48 vs 24-48 h	24-48 vs 0-24 h	>48 h	24-48 h	0-24 h
Protein Coding	76.7	77.1	75.5	78.7	78.1
Ig	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.0
TcR	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2
lncRNA	13.5	13.7	14.8	12.3	13.4
Non-coding RNA	0.7	1.6	1.5	1.1	1.6
TEC	1.0	1.1	0.9	0.5	0.8
Pseudogene	7.9	6.2	7.1	5.8	5.9

Whole Blood	>48 vs 24-48 h	24-48 vs 0-24 h	>48 h	24-48 h	0-24 h
Protein Coding	60.1	61.7	56.4	64.6	67.7
Ig	0.4	0.0	0.9	0.8	1.3
TcR	0.4	0.3	0.9	0.8	0.7
lncRNA	22.0	23.6	22.9	18.1	17.5
Non-coding RNA	1.1	1.8	1.8	2.7	1.6
TEC	4.4	2.1	3.5	0.4	2.3
Pseudogene	11.7	10.6	13.2	10.0	8.9

Sup. Figure 2

Sup. Figure 3

Sup. Figure 4

Sup. Figure 5 A

Subject	Sex	IS cause	Age At Onset	Time since event (h)
tPA1 (MON, WB)	Male	SV	67	6.4
tPA2 (MON, NEU, WB)	Male	SV	84	13
tPA3 (MON, NEU, WB)	Male	LV	76	20.4
tPA4 (MON, NEU)	Male	SV	43	25.5
tPA5 (MON, WB)	Female	LV	62	58.3

■ 0-24 h
 ■ >24 h
 ■ tPA
 ■ No tPA

Sup. Figure 6

A

Monocytes

B

Neutrophils

C

Whole Blood

Sup. Figure 7

Transcriptome dynamics

Differential expression

Co-expression networks

Key genes and pathways associated with time after ischemic stroke